

Dogs and Cats Image Detection using CNN

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Abstract —Image or object recognition system has commonly used in many sector. The purpose of this system is for the system to identify and distinguish objects. This research contains how computers identify images of dogs and cats based on available training data and test data. The purpose of this study is to find out how accurately the computer can distinguish the original object and other objects that resemble the original object in the given test data. The method that used in this research are Relu, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, and Selu. The configurations used in this research were step per epoch 30, epochs 50, and validation steps 35. The highest training accuracy value was obtained by the Softsign method with a value of 0.75. The highest validation accuracy value was obtained by the Relu without data augmentation method with a value of 0.75. The highest training loss value was obtained by the Selu method without data augmentation with a value of 8.40 and the highest validation loss value was obtained by the Selu method without data augmentation with a value of 8.18. The lowest training accuracy value was obtained by the Sigmoid method with data augmentation with a value of 0.45. The lowest validation accuracy value was obtained by the Sigmoid method without data augmentation with a value of 0.46. The lowest training loss value was obtained by the Relu method with a value of 0.56. and the lowest validation loss value was obtained by the Relu method with a value of 0.51. From these results, it can be concluded that the high or low results of training accuracy, validation accuracy, training loss, and validation loss depend on the method and configuration carried out.

Keywords—Image recognition, Object recognition, Relu, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, Selu.

I. INTRODUCTION

Image or object recognition system has commonly used in many sector. Not just implemented in research, this system has been implemented in various fields such as education, industry, games, and banking. Image classification came into existence for decreasing the gap between the computer vision and human vision by training the computer with the data. [1] The purpose of this system is for the system to identify and distinguish objects. [2].

This research contains how computers identify images of dogs and cats based on available training data and test data. The purpose of this study is to find out how accurately the computer can distinguish the original object and other objects that resemble the original object in the given test data.

II. RELATED WORKS

Some studies related to image detection or object detection include research on image recognition using machine learning by Abhinav et al. The result of the study was obtained using custom neural networks with the architecture of Convolution Neural Networks and Keras API.

In addition, related research has also been carried out by Oscar Lorente et al on the classification of images with deep learning techniques. The results obtained are the results of the accuracy obtained largely dependent on the model and configuration used in the study.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

The data used in this study came from several sources. The training data is obtained from the package code that has loaded the code and the training data from Stackoverflow. While the test data is obtained from various sources on the internet with the help of the Google search engine.

B. Methodology

There are 6 types of methods used in this study, namely Relu, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softplus, Softsign, and Selu. From these methods, it will be compared regarding the accuracy and loss of each method. The configurations used in this study were step per epoch 30, epochs 50, and validation steps 35.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Relu

Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results of the Relu method without augmentation data are as follows.

Fig 1. Training and Validation Accuracy (Relu without data augmentation)

Fig 2. Training and Validation Loss (Relu without data augmentation)

The results obtained without augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.70
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.75
- Highest Train. Loss: 0.70
- Highest Val. Loss: 0.74
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.49
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.48
- Lowest Train. Loss: 0.56
- Lowest Val. Loss: 0.51

In comparison, testing was also carried out with augmentation data and the following results were obtained.

Fig 3. Training and Validation Accuracy (Relu with data augmentation)

Fig 4. Training and Validation Loss (Relu with data augmentation)

The results obtained with the augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.70
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.73
- Highest Train. Loss: 0.70
- Highest Val. Loss: 0.74
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.47
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.50
- Lowest Train. Loss: 0.56
- Lowest Val. Loss: 0.51

B. Sigmoid

Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results of the Sigmoid method without augmentation data are as follows.

Fig 5. Training and Validation Accuracy (Sigmoid without data augmentation)

Fig 6. Training and Validation Loss (Sigmoid without data augmentation)

The results obtained without augmentation data are

Highest Train. Acc: 0.55
 Highest Val. Acc: 0.53
 Highest Train. Loss: 0.85
 Highest Val. Loss: 0.75
 Lowest Train. Acc: 0.46
 Lowest Val. Acc: 0.46
 Lowest Train. Loss: 0.69
 Lowest Val. Loss: 0.69

In comparison, testing was also carried out with augmentation data and the following results were obtained.

Fig 7. Training and Validation Accuracy (Sigmoid with data augmentation)

Fig 8. Training and Validation Loss (Sigmoid with data augmentation)

The results obtained with the augmentation data are

Highest Train. Acc: 0.53
 Highest Val. Acc: 0.52
 Highest Train. Loss: 0.82
 Highest Val. Loss: 0.83
 Lowest Train. Acc: 0.45
 Lowest Val. Acc: 0.47
 Lowest Train. Loss: 0.69
 Lowest Val. Loss: 0.69

C. Softmax

Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results of the Softmax method without augmentation data are as follows.

Fig 9. Training and Validation Accuracy (Softmax without data augmentation)

Fig 10. Training and Validation Loss (Softmax without data augmentation)

The results obtained without augmentation data are

Highest Train. Acc: 0.53
 Highest Val. Acc: 0.53
 Highest Train. Loss: 0.69
 Highest Val. Loss: 0.69
 Lowest Train. Acc: 0.45
 Lowest Val. Acc: 0.47
 Lowest Train. Loss: 0.69
 Lowest Val. Loss: 0.69

In comparison, testing was also carried out with augmentation data and the following results were obtained.

Fig 11. Training and Validation Accuracy (Softmax with data augmentation)

Fig 13. Training and Validation Accuracy (Softplus without data augmentation)

Fig 12. Training and Validation Loss (Softmax with data augmentation)

Fig 14. Training and Validation Loss (Softplus without data augmentation)

The results obtained with the augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.54
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Train. Loss: 0.69
- Highest Val. Loss: 0.69
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.46
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.48
- Lowest Train. Loss: 0.69
- Lowest Val. Loss: 0.69

D. Softplus

Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results of the Softplus method without augmentation data are as follows.

The results obtained without augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Train. Loss: 0.84
- Highest Val. Loss: 0.81
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.45
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.47
- Lowest Train. Loss: 0.72
- Lowest Val. Loss: 0.72

In comparison, testing was also carried out with augmentation data and the following results were obtained.

Fig 15. Training and Validation Accuracy (Softplus with data augmentation)

Fig 17. Training and Validation Accuracy (Softsign without data augmentation)

Fig 16. Training and Validation Loss (Softplus with data augmentation)

Fig 18. Training and Validation Loss (Softsign without data augmentation)

The results obtained with the augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Train. Loss: 0.81
- Highest Val. Loss: 0.81
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.47
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.47
- Lowest Train. Loss: 0.72
- Lowest Val. Loss: 0.72

The results obtained without augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.75
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.75
- Highest Train. Loss: 8.10
- Highest Val. Loss: 7.98
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.47
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.99
- Lowest Train. Loss: 0.98
- Lowest Val. Loss: 0.72

E. Softsign

Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results of the Softsign method without augmentation data are as follows.

In comparison, testing was also carried out with augmentation data and the following results were obtained.

Fig 19. Training and Validation Accuracy (Softsign with data augmentation)

Fig 20. Training and Validation Loss (Softsign with data augmentation)

The results obtained with the augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.68
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.71
- Highest Train. Loss: 0.80
- Highest Val. Loss: 0.93
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.49
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.49
- Lowest Train. Loss: 0.66
- Lowest Val. Loss: 0.60

F. Selu

Based on the tests that have been carried out, the results of the Selu method without augmentation data are as follows.

Fig 21. Training and Validation Accuracy (Selu without data augmentation)

Fig 22. Training and Validation Loss (Selu without data augmentation)

The results obtained without augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.56
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Train. Loss: 8.40
- Highest Val. Loss: 8.18
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.45
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.47
- Lowest Train. Loss: 6.79
- Lowest Val. Loss: 7.15

In comparison, testing was also carried out with augmentation data and the following results were obtained.

Fig 23. Training and Validation Accuracy (Selu with data augmentation)

Fig 24. Training and Validation Loss (Selu with data augmentation)

The results obtained with the augmentation data are

- Highest Train. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Val. Acc: 0.53
- Highest Train. Loss: 8.18
- Highest Val. Loss: 7.95
- Lowest Train. Acc: 0.46
- Lowest Val. Acc: 0.47
- Lowest Train. Loss: 7.13
- Lowest Val. Loss: 7.15th

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of trials that have been carried out from the Relu, Sigmoid, Softmax, Softsign, Softplus, and Selu methods, the following results were obtained. The highest training accuracy value was obtained by the Softsign method with a value of 0.75. The highest validation accuracy value was obtained by the Relu without data augmentation method with a value of 0.75. The highest training loss value was obtained by the Selu method without data augmentation with a value of 8.40 and the highest validation loss value was obtained by the Selu method without data augmentation with a value of 8.18.

The lowest training accuracy value was obtained by the Sigmoid method with data augmentation with a value of 0.45. The lowest validation accuracy value was obtained by the Sigmoid method without data augmentation with a value of 0.46. The lowest training loss value was obtained by the Relu method with a value of 0.56. and the lowest validation loss value was obtained by the Relu method with a value of 0.51.

From these results, it can be concluded that the high or low results of training accuracy, validation accuracy, training loss, and validation loss depend on the method and configuration carried out.

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